

STATEMENT:

this is the pre-print version of the article, “Member States' Constitutional Rules on the Withdrawal from the European Union: Spain”, in ERPL/REDP, vol. 31, no 1, spring/printemps 2019, pp. 283-328.

MEMBER STATES' CONSTITUTIONAL RULES
ON THE WITHDRAWAL FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION:
SPAIN¹

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Abstract

This article studies the legal framework that would apply in Spain in case it were to hypothetically decide to withdraw from the European Union. First, it will delve into the constitutional foundations of a hypothetical withdrawal, highlighting the controversies still alive today. Second, the article will analyze the procedure to be followed when denouncing an international treaty. Third, a special focus will be put on the possibility to conduct a hypothetical referendum on this matter and the legal effects and controversies arising from the possibility of conducting this type of consultation. Last, this research will endeavor to outline the issue of public opinion on the withdrawal from the European Union, signaling whether this matter is a topic of discussion in Spain nowadays, the political parties supporting such withdrawal, and whether civil society in Spain shows feelings of attachment to the EU or supports a move away from the institution.

Keywords

Spain-European Union-denunciation of international treaty- referendum-public opinion

¹ All translations are the responsibility of the author. For the purposes of accuracy, the Spanish text has been provided in footnote.

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I. Introduction

This article aims to analyze the legal framework applicable in case Spain were to decide hypothetically to withdraw from the European Union. It will depart from an analysis of the constitutional foundations of a hypothetical withdrawal. For this purpose, the legal provisions and the many issues arising from legal gaps left unresolved in the Constitution and later covered by the Law will be considered, highlighting the many controversies, still subject to public scrutiny and debate nowadays. Once the legal provisions and the main issues arising from the legal framework are examined, this study will move on to the procedure when denouncing an international treaty. First, it will consider the power to initiate this process, second, the required authorization by the Parliament, third the authority vested with the capacity to formalize the consent of the State and last, the participation of the Autonomous Communities in the process.

Once the constitutional framework has been outlined, the controversial possibility to conduct a hypothetical referendum will be addressed. The study will mainly consider the different types of referendums permitted in the Spanish Constitution, the typology of referendum this consultation falls into, the requirements a consultation of this nature will need to comply with, and the legal effects and controversies arising from the possibility of conducting this type of consultation.

Last, this research will endeavor to outline the issue of public opinion on the withdrawal from the European Union, signaling whether it is a topic of discussion in Spain nowadays, the political parties supporting such withdrawal, and whether civil society in Spain shows feelings of attachment to the EU or supports a move away from the institution.

This article hopes to shed light on the law and the process and the debates surrounding international institutional law, the current phenomenon of moving away from institutions, specifically the European Union, in Spain. It endeavors to highlight legal vacuums, unclear mechanisms embedded in the procedure when withdrawing, current legal debates and political developments in Spain that, considered globally, show a pattern that needs utmost attention from the international community.

II. Constitutional Foundations of a hypothetical withdrawal of Spain from the European Union

1. The Specific provisions on EU withdrawal in the Constitution

The relationship between international law and national law in Spain is regulated by article 93 to 96 of the Spanish Constitution of 1978. Article 93³ requires that the conclusion of treaties by which it is attributed to an organization or international institution the exercise of powers derived from the Constitution needs to be authorized through an organic law⁴. The General Courts or the Government, as the case may be, needs to guarantee the fulfillment of these treaties and decisions issued by the international or supranational organization holder of the cession.

Following article 93, article 94⁵ constitutionalizes another type of international treaty, not delegating powers to an international organization, but requiring a specific procedure when treaties are drafted and when their material scope extends to treaties of a political nature, of a military nature, affecting the territorial integrity of the State or the fundamental rights and duties established in Title I, involving financial obligations for the Public Treasury and involving modification or repeal of any law or requiring legislative measures for its execution. Article 94.1 requires that these treaties or agreements need the prior authorization of the Parliament (*Cortes Generales*). Article

³ Artículo 93: Mediante ley orgánica se podrá autorizar la celebración de tratados por los que se atribuya a una organización o institución internacional el ejercicio de competencias derivadas de la Constitución. Corresponde a las Cortes Generales o al Gobierno, según los casos, la garantía del cumplimiento de estos tratados y de las resoluciones emanadas de los organismos internacionales o supranacionales titulares de la cesión.

⁴ An Organic Law is a specific type of law issued by the Parliament, where approval, modification or repeal requires an absolute majority of the Congress of Deputies, in a final vote on the whole proposal. Organic laws are those related to the development of fundamental rights and public liberties, those that approve the Statutes of Autonomy and the general electoral regime and others expressly provided for in the Constitution (Article 81 of the Spanish Constitution). In these matters there is no legislative delegation in committees (Article 75.3 Spanish Constitution) or in the Government (Article 82.1 Spanish Constitution), nor the popular legislative initiative (Article 87.3 Spanish Constitution).

⁵ Artículo 94 1. La prestación del consentimiento del Estado para obligarse por medio de tratados o convenios requerirá la previa autorización de las Cortes Generales, en los siguientes casos:

- a) Tratados de carácter político.
- b) Tratados o convenios de carácter militar.
- c) Tratados o convenios que afecten a la integridad territorial del Estado o a los derechos y deberes fundamentales establecidos en el Título I.
- d) Tratados o convenios que impliquen obligaciones financieras para la Hacienda Pública.
- e) Tratados o convenios que supongan modificación o derogación de alguna ley o exijan medidas legislativas para su ejecución.

2. El Congreso y el Senado serán inmediatamente informados de la conclusión de los restantes tratados o convenios.

94.2 establishes that remaining treaties (those not included in article 94.1) will require that the Government immediately inform the Congress and the Senate of their conclusion.

Following article 94, article 95⁶ foresees the possibility of constitutional review of the conclusion of an international treaty that contains clauses contrary to the Constitution. The possibility to request a constitutional review is attributed to the Government or either of the Chambers of the Parliament, the Congress or the Senate, which will give the possibility to the Constitutional Court to declare whether or not there is such a normative conflict.

It is article 96 of the Constitution that considers the possibility to withdraw from an international treaty. Article 96⁷ requires that those treaties validly concluded, once officially published in Spain, will be part of the internal order. Its provisions may only be repealed, modified or suspended in the manner provided in the treaties themselves or in accordance with the general rules of international law. Article 96.2 establishes that for the denunciation of international treaties and conventions, the same procedure, foreseen for their approval in article 94, will be the one to be followed.

2. Issues arising from the Constitutional framework

The Constitution left many issues unresolved in relation to the withdrawal from an International Organization under article 93. This was also due to the fact that, at the time of the Constitution, in 1978, many developments in International Law were unthinkable. In relation to the possibility to withdraw unilaterally from a treaty, article 96.2 firstly considered only denunciation as a form of termination, second, it directed to the procedure under article 94. Yet, did not define what denunciation meant, left unresolved how to terminate a treaty of the kind covered by article 93, treaties delegating powers to International Organizations i.e. the European

⁶ Artículo 95 1. La celebración de un tratado internacional que contenga estipulaciones contrarias a la Constitución exigirá la previa revisión constitucional.2. El Gobierno o cualquiera de las Cámaras puede requerir al Tribunal Constitucional para que declare si existe o no esa contradicción.

⁷ Artículo 96 1. Los tratados internacionales válidamente celebrados, una vez publicados oficialmente en España, formarán parte del ordenamiento interno. Sus disposiciones sólo podrán ser derogadas, modificadas o suspendidas en la forma prevista en los propios tratados o de acuerdo con las normas generales del Derecho internacional.2. Para la denuncia de los tratados y convenios internacionales se utilizará el mismo procedimiento previsto para su aprobación en el artículo 94.

Union and third, did not specify the procedure to be followed when directing to article 94, since article 94.1 contemplates a different procedure to article 94.2 treaties⁸.

These constitutional deficits were solved through the Regulations of the Congress⁹ and the Senate¹⁰ and in 2014, by the adoption of Law 25/2014, of Treaties and International Agreements of November 27th (from now on Law 25/2014)¹¹. In its Preliminary Statements (*Exposición de Motivos*) the Law refers to the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties of May 23, 1969, as the “Treaty of treaties” and the reflection of customary law in this area¹².

Before 2014, the only specific norm regulating treaties in Spain was Decree 801/1972, of March 24, on the Organization of the Activity of the State Administration in Matters of International Treaties, however, with the passing of time, Decree 801/1972, of March 24, became obsolete due to the development experienced by International Law and because of the profound political and constitutional changes experienced by Spain.¹³ The Law mentions several important changes experiences by Spain internationally and nationally from 1972 onwards: first, the increase of international organizations with the capacity, in many cases, to conclude international agreements with States, being particularly noteworthy the example of the European Union, with broad competences in foreign matters, having consequences for the Member States, because of the peculiar and complex category of mixed agreements with third countries.¹⁴ Second, intensity and complexity of practice in conventional matters, which has given rise to new forms of agreements and new problems of application.¹⁵ Third, from the internal perspective, regulatory vacuums had been covered meanwhile, in practice, by, first, the issuance of circulars and ministerial orders articulating in a dispersed manner the procedures to be followed in the internal processing of

⁸ Remiro Brotons, A., “Artículo 96: Tratados Internacionales como parte del ordenamiento interno” en Oscar Alzaga Villaamil, O., 2006, *Comentarios a la Constitución Española*, Edersa, p. 644-646

⁹ Resolución de 24 de febrero de 1982 por la que se ordena la publicación en el «Boletín Oficial del Estado» del nuevo Reglamento del Congreso de los Diputados. «BOE» núm. 55, de 05/03/1982 <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1982-5196&tn=2&p=19940618>

¹⁰ Texto refundido del Reglamento del Senado aprobado por la Mesa del Senado, oída la Junta de Portavoces, en su reunión del día 3 de mayo de 1994. «BOE» núm. 114, de 13/05/1994. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1994-10830&p=20170315&tn=2>

¹¹ Ley 25/2014, de 27 de noviembre, de Tratados y otros Acuerdos Internacionales. «BOE» núm. 288, de 28 de noviembre de 2014, https://boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2014-12326

¹² *Ibid*, Exposición de Motivos I

¹³ *Ibid*, Exposición de Motivos II, mainly referring to the end of Franco’s dictatorship, and the advent of democracy in 1978.

¹⁴ *Ibid*

¹⁵ *Ibid*

international treaties and other possible international agreements, second, the interpreting task of the Constitutional Court, as well as the advisory work of the Council of State and the International Legal Department of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Cooperation, and third, the work of ordinary judges.¹⁶ Fourth, the territorial design of the State carried out after the entry into force of the Spanish Constitution of 1978, entailing the recognition of the Autonomous Communities, through their respective Statutes of Autonomy, having relevant competences in matters of external action.¹⁷

Article 2 u) of Law 25/2014 defines “denunciation” as an act by which Spain states its consent to terminate the obligations derived from a treaty with respect to itself.¹⁸ In this sense the law defines denunciation, which the Constitution hadn’t defined in 1978. Yet, Spain had ratified years earlier the VCLT¹⁹, which provides for denunciation as a form of termination of treaties in article 42. 2: “The termination of a treaty, its denunciation or the withdrawal of a party may take place only as a result of the application of the provisions of the treaty or of this Convention”. The VCLT didn’t define denunciation, nevertheless this term has been clarified by the United Nations, where denunciation and withdrawal are used interchangeably and express the same legal concept, to refer to a unilateral act by which a nation, that is currently a party to a treaty, ends its membership to that treaty²⁰.

Chapter V of Law 25/2014, under the title “Amendment, denunciation and suspension of international treaties”, includes article 37²¹, specific to the denunciation of an international treaty.

¹⁶ *Ibid*

¹⁷ *Ibid*

¹⁸ Artículo 2. Definiciones. A los efectos de esta Ley se entiende por: u) «denuncia»: acto por el que España hace constar su consentimiento para dar por finalizadas respecto a sí mismo las obligaciones derivadas de un tratado.

¹⁹ Instrumento de adhesión de 2 de mayo de 1972, del Convenio de Viena sobre el Derecho de los Tratados, adoptado en Viena el 23 de mayo de 1969. «BOE» núm. 142, de 13 de junio de 1980

²⁰ UN Office of Legal Affairs, Final Clauses of Multilateral Treaties Handbook (UN Sales No E04V3 2003) (‘Final Clauses Handbook’) 109

²¹ Artículo 37. Denuncia y suspensión.

1. El Consejo de Ministros podrá acordar la denuncia o la suspensión de la aplicación de un tratado internacional, a propuesta del Ministro de Asuntos Exteriores y de Cooperación, en coordinación con el ministerio competente por razón de la materia objeto del tratado, conforme a las normas del propio tratado o a las normas generales de Derecho Internacional.

2. Por razones de urgencia, debidamente justificadas, el Ministro de Asuntos Exteriores y de Cooperación, y en su caso, en coordinación con el ministerio competente en relación con la materia objeto del tratado, podrá decidir la suspensión de la aplicación de un tratado, y recabará con carácter inmediato la aprobación del Consejo de Ministros.

3. No obstante, lo dispuesto en los apartados anteriores, los tratados internacionales comprendidos en los artículos 93 y 94.1 de la Constitución Española solo podrán ser denunciados previa autorización de las Cortes Generales, de conformidad con lo dispuesto en el artículo 96.2 de la Constitución Española.

Article 37 sets forth that “[t]he Council of Ministers may agree on the denunciation or suspension of the application of an international treaty, at the proposal of the Minister of Foreign Affairs and Cooperation, in coordination with the competent ministry by reason of the subject matter of the treaty, in accordance with the norms of the treaty itself or of the general norms of International Law [...] 3. [...] international treaties included in articles 93 and 94.1 of the Spanish Constitution may only be denounced upon authorization of the Parliament, in accordance with the provisions of article 96.2 of the Spanish Constitution. 4. The Government shall immediately inform the Parliament of the denunciation [...] of an international treaty”.

Leaving aside the procedure to withdraw from an international treaty, which will be considered in the next section, Law 25/2014 solved the legal gap present in the Constitution which had left article 93 treaties uncovered by a withdrawal clause. In this sense, article 37 of the Law clearly indicates that the procedure to withdraw from article 93 treaties will need the authorization from the Parliament, in accordance with the provisions of article 96.2 of the Constitution. In this sense, article 96.2 indicates article 94 as the procedure to follow, and since it is required by the law that there be authorization by the Parliament, it is indirectly excluding article 94.2 procedure, which does not require it.

Being the procedure to be followed solved, a few issues that arise in relation to the European Union stem from the obligations acquired by the State that originate from primary, secondary law and third country agreements. In this sense, if Spain were to withdraw from the foundational treaties, what would happen with the law that has been validly published, and hence has become internal law?

Article 96.1 of the Constitution requires that those treaties validly concluded, once officially published in Spain, will be part of the internal order. Article 1.5 of the Civil Code states as well that “[t]he legal norms contained in international treaties will not be directly applicable in Spain as long as they have not become part of the internal legal order through their publication in the

4. El Gobierno informará inmediatamente a las Cortes Generales de la denuncia o de la suspensión de la aplicación de un tratado internacional.

5. Cuando se acuerde la suspensión de la aplicación de un tratado internacional cuya autorización haya sido aprobada por las Cortes Generales, el Gobierno solicitará con carácter inmediato la ratificación de la suspensión por éstas. Si las Cortes Generales no aprobaran esta ratificación, el Gobierno revocará el acuerdo de suspensión de la aplicación del tratado.

“Official State Gazette”²². In relation to EU law the reception or insertion of the Treaties of the Union followed the procedure indicated in article 96.1 of the Constitution. All the Treaties that make up the EU, once ratified, became part of the Law applicable in Spain. The accession treaty to the European Union entered into force on January 1, 1986, as agreed, and on that date all the Treaties establishing the Communities were published in the Official Gazette (*Boletín Oficial del Estado*). The direct efficacy and opposability for individuals is completed from the internal publication of the legal text, thus displaying the fullness of internal effects.²³ On the other hand, the Constitution is silent on the issue of secondary law, after accession, yet, since acts of secondary law fall on competences attributed to the EU, the publication of EU acts will be opposable once published in the Official Gazette of the European Union, according to article 297 TFEU.²⁴

Once primary and secondary law is published, directly or by transposing it, it will become part of internal law. Article 96.1 of the Constitution requires that provisions of treaties validly concluded and officially published in Spain, may only be repealed, modified or suspended in the manner provided in the treaties themselves or in accordance with the general rules of international law. The Vienna Convention of 1969 recognized, with a general character, the procedures for the modification or termination of treaties in article 42.2: “The termination of a treaty, its denunciation or the withdrawal of a party, may take place only as a result of the application of the provisions of the treaty or of the present Convention”. Article 96.1 of the Constitution though, is not clear as far as the order that needs to be followed, allowing for derogation, modification or suspension to be done in an alternative way: “in the manner foreseen in the treaties themselves” or “in accordance with the general norms of international law”. In this sense, the Spanish Constitution did not include an explicit and clear mention of the relationship between international law and national law, or the hierarchical order *inter se*²⁵. Yet article 96 clearly sets forth that this group of norms, derived from

²² Artículo 1.5 del Código Civil: Las normas jurídicas contenidas en los tratados internacionales no serán de aplicación directa en España en tanto no hayan pasado a formar parte del ordenamiento interno mediante su publicación íntegra en el «Boletín Oficial del Estado».

²³ Martín, A. M., & Noguerras, D. J. L. (2017). *Instituciones y derecho de la Unión Europea*. Tecnos, p. 469-470. The requirement of publication has been a matter of much controversy. On the scholarly debate on this matter see Andrés de Santamaría, Paz, “Artículo 96”, en Casas Baamonde, M.E., y Rodríguez Piñero y Bravo Ferrer, M., (2008). *Comentarios a la Constitución*. Wolters Kluwer.

²⁴ *Ibid*

²⁵ Arroyo Lara indicates that both the German Constitution in its articles 25 and 5, the Italian Constitution in article 10 and the Spanish Republican Constitution of 1931 in its article 7, made an express reference to international law. Arroyo Lara, E. (1987). “Consideraciones sobre el alcance y contenido del artículo 96.1. «in fine» de la Constitución española”. *Revista Española de Derecho Internacional*, 405-421. This author expresses a preference of a national norm in which the function of general International Law is explicitly and clearly recognized with respect to domestic

international treaties, cannot be modified, repealed or suspended by internal rules, since the Constitution in this same article directly excludes this possibility²⁶. In this sense, Article 96.1 does not specify whether, in case of derogation, modification or suspension of the conventional norm, the provisions of the treaty's norms should prevail and be governed by general international law. Some authors have argued that, due to the order in which they appear in the article and the principle of "*lex specialis derogat lex generalis*", the norms of the treaty must be applied and those of International Law will remain subsidiary, when the treaties do not say anything about the particular. However, in the event that the treaty rules are unclear, or have a dubious interpretation, international law will have to replace the treaty and may even be applied with preference.²⁷

In relation to secondary law and third country agreements of the European Union, once validly published, will need to follow article 96.1 of the Constitution for their repeal, modification or suspension if Spain were to withdraw from the European Union. In this sense, article 70 of the VCLT would be the one applicable. Article 70 of the VCLT establishes that on the “consequences of the termination of a treaty” [...] unless the treaty otherwise provides or the parties otherwise agree, the termination of a treaty under its provisions or in accordance with the present Convention: (a) Releases the parties from any obligation further to perform the treaty; (b) Does not affect any right, obligation or legal situation of the parties created through the execution of the treaty prior to its termination. 2. If a State denounces or withdraws from a multilateral treaty, paragraph 1 applies in the relations between that State and each of the other parties to the treaty from the date when such denunciation or withdrawal takes effect”. It is important to highlight that article 70 clearly states that termination does not affect any right, obligation or legal situation of the parties created through the execution of the treaty prior to its termination. Hence, if Spain were to withdraw, since

law, and that is even better, if the degree of insertion and applicability of these rules is added quoting Calamia “ A questo punto riteniamo opportuno porci il quesito se, in definitiva, la formulazione espressa del procedimento di adattamento (sia ese globale, oppur seletivo) sia da preferiré ad una norma non scritta. E crediamo cha a tale domanda si debba risponeder in maniera positiva...una statuizione relativa all’adattamento rappresanti una maggiore garanzia di coerenza e di uniformazione dell’ordinamento statale al diritto internazionale generale...Se, poi, oltre che a regolare il fatto dell’adattamento, la norma costituzionale regola la modalitá concreta di esso ed indica il rango delle norme immesse, l’intensitá della garanzia raggiungerá il massimo...” Calamia, A. (1977). L’adattamento del diritto interno al diritto internazionale consuetudinario nelle piú recenti Costituzioni. *Rivista di Diritto Internazionale*, 59-74, p. 74 in Arroyo Lara, E., 1987, p. 407.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ *Ibid*, p. 48,

it is a party to the VCLT, it would be bound by article 70 and would be obliged to respect those rights and obligations created during its life as a party to the European Union.²⁸

Once Spain has withdrawn from the European Union, it is unclear, knowing that primary and secondary law have become internal law, due to its direct application or because of it being transposed, what will happen to this specific law that once originated from the European institutions. Article 70 of the VCLT clearly states that unless the treaty otherwise provides or the parties otherwise agree, the termination of a treaty under its provisions or in accordance with the present Convention releases the parties from any obligation further to perform the treaty. In this sense, the legal framework applicable to withdrawal will need to be established in a hypothetical withdrawal agreement. This withdrawal agreement will probably be influenced by the precedent set by the UK when withdrawing and the creation of a specific category in internal law denominated “retained EU law”²⁹ and will depend on the negotiation of the parties to the agreement.

The status of this category is at the time of this writing difficult to foresee. Based on the problems and challenges faced by the Exit Agreement between the UK and the European Union, it is unclear how this category of law will be repealed, modified or suspended³⁰, and who will have

²⁸ Mangas Martín, A. (2016). *¿Brexit? Escenarios internacionales y Gibraltar*. Real Instituto Elcano, 1-16, p. 13-14. http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/portal/rielcano_es/contenido?WCM_GLOBAL_CONTEXT=/elcano/elcano_es/zonas_es/dt9-2016-mangas-brexit-escenarios-internacionales-gibraltar

²⁹ Retained EU law is a new category created in the Brexit withdrawal agreement. It is a residual body of law. Its purpose is to preserve, so far as is possible, the domestic effect of EU law as it stands on exit day. Retained EU law is defined as “anything that is retained by virtue of subsections 2, 3 or 4 of the EUWA”. Under the Agreement EU law is “retained” if it falls within three categories stipulated by the European Union (Withdrawal) Act. Those categories are: EU-derived domestic legislation (section 2); direct EU-legislation (section 3); other rights and obligations (etc.) arising from section 2(1) of the ECA (section 4). The EUWA notably and specifically excludes from retained EU law: the principle of supremacy of EU law (in relation to future enactments or rule of law); the Charter on Fundamental Rights (except insofar as rights are replicated in instruments of retained EU law anyway); and the “Francovich” state liability principle of EU law (for acts or omissions arising after exit day or not litigated within 2 years of it). The EUWA does not retain from EU law the category of EU legislation called “directives”. Directives set common objectives for Member states but leave discretion as to the manner of implementation on a national level, unlike regulations which apply and are directly effective across all Member states. This means they are not “directly applicable”. Through a combination of sections 2 and 4 EUWA, domestic legislation that implements directives (i.e. EU-derived domestic legislation) has been preserved, as have: any rights and obligations [arising from an EU directive] of a kind recognised by the European Court or any court or tribunal in the United Kingdom in a case decided before exit day (s. 4(2) (b) EUWA). Some of those rights and/or obligations may have been conferred by EU directives, and will be preserved under the EUWA.

<http://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8375/CBP-8375.pdf>, p. 17.

³⁰ “The European Union (Withdrawal) Act only preserves the legal effect of EU law on exit day only as a starting point, however. Whether and how this body of law will change in the future is at least as important as what the substance of it is at the point the UK formally leaves the European Union. Except for domestic implementing legislation (which will now become “EU derived domestic legislation”) no part of what will become “retained EU

the competence to decide a conflict between this category of law and internal law. In this sense, the Spanish Constitutional Court has recognized the principle of primacy of European Union Law over national law, its incapacity to decide on matters of conflict, and conditions the application of national law to the referral of the matter by a national judge to a preliminary ruling³¹. If Spain were to withdraw, primacy of EU law would be at stake, since it would be highly improbable that the State, if it wishes to keep the primacy principle, which is cornerstone of the IO it wishes to leave.

Consequently, Spanish authorities will have to decide on the role of the European Union Court of Justice³² to interpret conflicts between the law that is retained and internal law. If Spain complies with article 70 of the VCLT, it would be advisable that the withdrawal agreement maintain the European Court of Justice' jurisdiction over those matters where Spain is committed to comply with the EU rules it decides to preserve (on citizens' rights, customs, etc.)³³, since for the purposes of international cooperation, an international body can be more capable of considering all interests at stake. Nevertheless, jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice is not a given, and it will be a matter that will depend on the negotiating authorities.

law” will have been susceptible to domestic modification while the UK is a Member state of the EU. For Parliament to so modify, or for Governments to be able to so modify, would have been against the principle of EU law supremacy that underpins the Treaties. As retained EU law is a domestically transposed “equivalent”, rather than EU law itself, however, Parliament will assume the ultimate constitutional control over its content and its status in relation to domestic law more generally. Unless and to the extent that subsequent primary legislation provides otherwise, this law will be able to be modified (or even repealed) by future Acts of Parliament from exit day onwards.⁴¹ In some circumstances, retained EU law will also be modifiable (or indeed susceptible to repeal) by secondary legislation. This secondary legislation will be made under, but need not be limited to being made under, the EUWA and other specific Brexit-related legislation (e.g. the Trade Bill)”. *Ibid*, p. 18

³¹ Sánchez Legido, A. (1991). Las relaciones entre el derecho comunitario y el derecho interno en la jurisprudencia del Tribunal Constitucional. *Revista Española de Derecho Constitucional*, 11; Mangas, A. (1991). La Constitución y la Ley ante el Derecho Comunitario (comentario a la sentencia del Tribunal Constitucional español 28/1991, de 14 de febrero, sobre la Ley Orgánica de Régimen Electoral General y el Acta relativa a las elecciones al Parlamento Europeo), *Revista de Instituciones Europeas*, vol. 18, 1991, p. 587-623, p. 602.

³² EU law depends on the case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union for its consistent interpretation and application. Article 267 TFEU provides a “preliminary reference” procedure, whereby the CJEU will give a ruling on the interpretation of EU law. It will do so where it is “necessary” to establish a point of EU law to dispose of a case in a national court. Once the UK leaves the EU, the Treaties will no longer apply to it and this reference procedure will lapse with respect to it. In any case, UK courts will be enforcing retained EU law (a purely domestic form of law) and not EU law itself. <http://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-8375/CBP-8375.pdf>, p. 43

³³ The same as is being negotiated in relation to Brexit: See Lock, Tobias: *On Thin Ice: the Role of the Court of Justice under the Withdrawal Agreement*, VerfBlog, 2018/11/15, <https://verfassungsblog.de/on-thin-ice-the-role-of-the-court-of-justice-under-the-withdrawal-agreement/>.

III. Constitutional Obstacles to Withdraw from the European Union

1. Constitutional framework applicable to the withdrawal of Spain from the European Union

1. Authority to initiate the denunciation of a treaty

Article 37 of Law 25/2014³⁴ indicates that the Council of Ministers may agree on the denunciation or suspension of the application of an international treaty, at the proposal of the Minister of Foreign Affairs and Cooperation, in coordination with the competent ministry by reason of the subject matter of the treaty, in accordance with the rules of the own treaty or to the general norms of International Law.

Article 37 solves an issue over which the Constitution remained silent: the authority entitled to initiate the denunciation of a Treaty. Yet even if the Constitution did not designate who was the entity with the authority to initiate the conclusion of a treaty or to denounce a treaty, article 97 of the Constitution clearly states that “[t]he Government directs the internal and external policy, the civil and military administration and the defense of the State. Exercises the executive function and the regulatory power in accordance with the Constitution and the laws”³⁵. Also the Decree 801/1972 of 24 March, on the Organization of the Activity of the State Administration regarding International Treaties³⁶, nowadays derogated, in relation to the negotiation, adoption and authentication of the text of a treaty, incorporated into article 9 the recognition of the competence of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to negotiate an international treaty and that in accordance with the provisions of article ten, fifth paragraph, of the Law on the Legal System of the State Administration, the competence of the Council of Ministers to authorize the negotiation of a treaty. The law points to the Minister of Foreign Affairs as having the responsibility to request the appropriate authorization³⁷.

³⁴ *Cit.*

³⁵ “El Gobierno dirige la política interior y exterior, la Administración civil y militar y la defensa del Estado. Ejerce la función ejecutiva y la potestad reglamentaria de acuerdo con la Constitución y las leyes”.

³⁶ Decreto 801/1972, de 24 de marzo, sobre ordenación de la actividad de la Administración del Estado en materia de Tratados Internacionales. «BOE» núm. 85, de 8 de abril de 1972, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-1972-531>

³⁷ Artículo nueve. Uno. La negociación de un tratado es de la competencia del Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores. Dos. De conformidad con lo establecido en el artículo diez, apartado quinto, de la Ley de Régimen Jurídico de la Administración del Estado, es de la competencia del Consejo de Ministros autorizar la negociación de un tratado. Corresponde al Ministro de Asuntos Exteriores solicitar la oportuna autorización.

Even with this prerogative, this competence has its limitations and is not completely discretionary. During this procedure, the Government's action will depend, on the report written by the International Legal Consultancy (*Asesoría Jurídica Internacional*) and the Opinion of the State Council (*Dictámen del Consejo de Estado*). Article 22.1 of the Organic Law 3/1980, of April 22nd, of the Council of State³⁸ states that the Permanent Commission of the Council of State should be consulted in all international treaties or agreements needing authorization from the Parliament prior to the provision of State consent³⁹. These reports are not binding on the Government, as article 2.2 of the Law clearly outlines, yet they condition the Government's freedom to act, since "in practice, the government does not separate itself from the opinion of the highest-ranking body of the Advisory Administration"⁴⁰.

Article 155⁴¹ of the Regulations of the Congress state that the Government will request from the Parliament the granting of such authorization by sending to the Congress of Deputies the corresponding agreement of the Council of Ministers together with the text of the treaty or agreement, as well as the Report that justifies the request and the reservations and declarations that the Government intends to formulate, where appropriate. The Congress will have to decide on granting the authorization and on the formulation of reservations and declarations proposed by the Government. The deadline for the submission is established in article 155.3, that requires that the Government submit to Congress within ninety days following the agreement of the Council of Ministers. This period, when justified, may be extended up to one hundred and eighty days. In this last case, and after the initial ninety days have elapsed, the Government will be obliged to send a communication to Congress justifying the delay⁴².

³⁸ Ley Orgánica 3/1980, de 22 de abril, del Consejo de Estado, «BOE» núm. 100, de 25/04/1980 <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1980-8648>

³⁹ Artículo veintidós. La Comisión Permanente del Consejo de Estado deberá ser consultada en los siguientes asuntos: Uno. En todos los tratados o convenios internacionales sobre la necesidad de autorización de las Cortes Generales con carácter previo a la prestación del consentimiento del Estado.

⁴⁰ Remiro Brotons, A., "artículos 93 y 94" en Oscar Alzaga Villaamil, O., 2006, Comentarios a la Constitución Española, Edersa, p. 526.

⁴¹ Artículo 155. 2. El Gobierno solicitará de las Cortes Generales la concesión de dicha autorización mediante el envío al Congreso de los Diputados del correspondiente acuerdo del Consejo de Ministros junto con el texto del tratado o convenio, así como la Memoria que justifique la solicitud y las reservas y declaraciones que el Gobierno pretendiere formular, en su caso. El Congreso deberá pronunciarse tanto acerca de la concesión de la autorización como sobre la formulación de reservas y declaraciones propuestas por el Gobierno.

⁴² Artículo 155. 3. La solicitud a que se refiere el apartado anterior será presentada por el Gobierno al Congreso, dentro de los noventa días siguientes al acuerdo del Consejo de Ministros, plazo que, en casos justificados, podrá ser ampliado

One additional aspect that needs to be considered is also the absolute prohibition of popular initiative in international matters. Popular initiative to commence legislative action is contemplated in article 87.3 of the Constitution. This article strictly attributes legislative initiative to the Government, the Congress and the Senate, in accordance with the Constitution and the Regulations of the Chambers. The Assemblies of the Autonomous Communities may request from the Government the adoption of a bill or refer a bill to the Congress Committee, delegating before said Chamber a maximum of three members of the Assembly in charge of their defense. Popular initiative for law proposals will be permitted and will be regulated by an Organic Law⁴³. Article 87.3 requires that the initiative be backed by no less than 500,000 accredited signatures will be required and ends with a bar to any popular initiative in matters specific to organic, tax or international law, nor in relation to the prerogative of grace.⁴⁴

2. Authorization by the Parliament

Article 96.2 of the Constitution, as mentioned earlier, establishes clearly that to terminate a treaty unilaterally, article 94 will apply. Since Law 25/2014 requires authorization from Parliament in case authorization were sought to unilaterally withdraw from article 93 treaties, as states earlier, the procedure in article 94.1 will apply.

Article 74.2 of the Constitution requires that decisions of the Parliaments set forth in articles 94.1 [...] shall be adopted by a majority of each of the Chambers. The article follows by requiring that, in the case of article 94.1 treaties, the procedure to decide on the authorization will be initiated by the Congress. If no agreement is reached, between the Senate and Congress, an attempt will be made to obtain it through a Mixed Commission, composed of the same number of Deputies and Senators. The Commission will present a text that will be voted by both Chambers. If it is not approved in the established manner, the Congress will decide by absolute majority⁴⁵. Article 74.2

hasta ciento ochenta días. En este último supuesto, y una vez transcurridos los noventa días iniciales, el Gobierno estará obligado a enviar al Congreso una comunicación motivando documentalmente el retraso.

⁴³ This law is the Ley Orgánica 3/1984, de 26 de marzo, Reguladora de la Iniciativa Legislativa Popular. «BOE» núm. 74, de 27/03/1984 <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1984-7249>

⁴⁴ Remiro Brotons, A., “artículos 93 y 94”, *vid supra* note 40, p. 644-646

⁴⁵ Artículo 74

1. Las Cámaras se reunirán en sesión conjunta para ejercer las competencias no legislativas que el Título II atribuye expresamente a las Cortes Generales.

2. Las decisiones de las Cortes Generales previstas en los artículos 94,1, 145,2, y 158, 2, se adoptarán por mayoría de cada una de las Cámaras. En el primer caso, el procedimiento se iniciará por el Congreso, y en los otros dos, por el Senado. En ambos casos, si no hubiera acuerdo entre Senado y Congreso, se intentará obtener por una Comisión Mixta compuesta de igual número de Diputados y Senadores. La Comisión

does not set a deadline for the Commission to present a common text to the Chambers, nor does it foresee the hypothesis that it is unable to achieve it.⁴⁶

Article 74.2 of the Spanish Constitution requires hence that decisions under article 94.1 be adopted by a majority of both Chambers. Yet there are different aspects that give more power to Congress in respect to the Senate: first, the fact that it is the Congress that will initiate a procedure of authorization of the denunciation an international treaty. Second, comparatively, the power given to the Senate in this process is weaker than the one granted to it through the legislative procedure foreseen in article 90 of the Spanish Constitution, since, in the latter, it gives the Senate a capacity to veto decisions of the Congress. Third, Congress is finally given the last word if the proposal by the Mixed Commission is not approved, and permits the authorization to pass when absolute majority is reached.

The Regulations of the Congress⁴⁷ regulate in articles 155 to 160 the procedure to be followed under article 94.1 CE. Under Title VII of said Regulations, on the granting of authorizations and other acts of Congress with direct legal effect, article 160, considers that in the event of denunciation of a treaty or agreement, the same procedure will be followed as that provided for the provision of consent to be bound by said treaty or agreement. Hence, the same procedure will be followed as when obtaining an authorization to be bound by a treaty. This procedure is detailed, starting from article 155.4, requiring that Congress reach an agreement in the following 60 days after receiving the request by the Government.⁴⁸ Article 156.1 of the Regulations points to the procedure to be followed in order to obtain an authorization: First, the procedure for Congress to grant an authorization will follow the common legislative procedure⁴⁹. Second, proposals presented by the Deputies and by the Parliamentary Groups will be considered as amendments to the totality in the following cases: When claiming the denial or deferral of the requested

presentará un texto que será votado por ambas Cámaras. Si no se aprueba en la forma establecida, decidirá el Congreso por mayoría absoluta.

⁴⁶ It has only happened once. See Remiro Brotons, A., “artículos 93 y 94”, *vid supra* note 40, p. 564.

⁴⁷ Resolución de 24 de febrero de 1982 por la que se ordena la publicación en el «Boletín Oficial del Estado» del nuevo Reglamento del Congreso de los Diputados. «BOE» núm. 55, de 05/03/1982 <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1982-5196&tn=2&p=19940618>

⁴⁸ “4. El acuerdo del Congreso deberá ser adoptado en un plazo de sesenta días”

⁴⁹ Common legislative procedure: García-Escudero Márquez, P. (2006). *El procedimiento legislativo ordinario en las Cortes Generales*. Centro de Estudios Políticos y Constitucionales; Gómez Lugo, Y. (2008). El procedimiento legislativo ordinario en las Cortes Generales. *Revista Española de Derecho Constitucional*, (83), 355-368. http://www.congreso.es/portal/page/portal/Congreso/Congreso/Hist_Normas/Norm/Reglam/T5/T5Cap2

authorization; when they propose reservations or declarations and these were not foreseen by the treaty or agreement. The proposals presented by the Deputies and by the Parliamentary Groups will have the consideration of amendments to the articles in the following cases: When they propose the suppression, addition or modification to the reservations or declarations that the Government intends to formulate and when formulating reservations or declarations provided by the treaty.

Based on the Regulations of the Senate⁵⁰, Section Seven regulates Treaties in articles 144 to 148. Article 144 limits clearly the role of the Senate in the decision making process. Proposals for non-ratification, postponement or reservations regarding international treaties and agreements that require the authorization of the Parliament may be submitted by the Senate. Article 144.1 states lastly that the text of the treaties cannot be amended. Article 144.2 requires that proposals that oppose the ratification of a treaty will be subject to the provisions for veto proposals. Article 144.3 states that the reservation proposals can only be formulated to the treaties and agreements that foresee this possibility or whose content admit it. These proposals, as well as those of postponement, will follow the procedure established for amendments in the ordinary legislative procedure. Article 144.4 compels that the competent Commission shall submit to the Plenary, in accordance with the general rules, a reasoned proposal on whether the requested authorization should be granted or not.

Clearly the Senate has a limited power in respect to the Congress in respect to the process to conclude treaties and hence, to denounce them⁵¹. The Senate is the Territorial Chamber of the Parliament and is responsible for giving voice and channeling the interests of the territorial entities. Nevertheless this visibility and presence does not require that the Senate's proposals or decisions be binding on the Congress. On the contrary, the strength of the Senate is very limited as a territorial chamber, since the two Chambers have no equal status. In relation to article 74.2 of the Constitution, it has a role for the authorization to conclude treaties, but, definitively, "it may aspire to delay the definitive decision, in the hands of Congress, and demand from it, for this, a reinforced

⁵⁰ Texto refundido del Reglamento del Senado aprobado por la Mesa del Senado, oída la Junta de Portavoces, en su reunión del día 3 de mayo de 1994. «BOE» núm. 114, de 13 de mayo de 1994. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-1994-10830>

⁵¹ This position is generalized and not only in cases of international relations and treaty conclusion. In this sense, the Spanish Parliamentary system has been described as a model of asymmetric bicameralism. <http://www.senado.es/web/conocersenado/temasclave/sistemabicameral/index.html>

majority”, meaning absolute majority in case there were to be no agreement after the establishment of the Joint Commission⁵². This seems evident from a comparative analysis of article 156 of the Regulations of the Congress and article 144 of the Regulations of the Senate. Both direct to the ordinary legislative procedure when denying or deferring the request, proposing reservations or declarations or including amendments. The role attributed to the Senate in the ordinary legislative procedure is clearly weak. Article 121 of the Regulations of the Congress requires that Bills passed by Congress and vetoed or amended by the Senate will be submitted to a new consideration by the Congress. Following, article 122, permits that in the event that the Senate has vetoed a bill, the text will be debated in Congress, and after the debate, the text initially approved by the Congress will be put to a vote and, if ratified by the favorable vote of the absolute majority of the members of the House, the veto will be lifted. If the initial text does not obtain such a majority, it shall be submitted again to a vote, two months after the filing of the veto. If, in this voting the project obtains a simple majority of the votes cast, the veto will also be lifted; otherwise, the project will be rejected. The amendments proposed by the Senate will be subject of debate and voting and will be incorporated into the text of the Congress when they obtain the simple majority of the votes cast, as required by article 123 of the Regulations.

Both Regulations require that in the event that during the processing of a treaty or agreement in the Congress of Deputies there are doubts about the constitutionality of any of its stipulations, the Plenary of the Congress, at the initiative of two Parliamentary Groups or a fifth of the Deputies, may agree to address the Constitutional Court. This requirement is provided for in Article 95.2 of the Constitution. Article 157 of the Regulations of the Congress require that the processing of the treaty or agreement will be interrupted and can only be resumed if the criterion of the Court is favorable to the constitutionality of the stipulations contained therein. Article 147⁵³ of the Regulations of the Senate as well require that the Chamber, at the proposal of a Parliamentary Group or of twenty-five Senators, may request the Constitutional Court to declare whether a Treaty or Convention, submitted for its consideration, is contrary to the Constitution or not. Once said

⁵² Remiro Brotons, A., “artículos 93 y 94”, vid supra note 40, p. 564.

⁵³ Artículo 147: La Cámara, a propuesta de un Grupo parlamentario o de veinticinco Senadores, podrá requerir al Tribunal Constitucional para que declare si un Tratado o Convenio, sometido a su consideración, es o no contrario a la Constitución. Acordado dicho requerimiento, se suspenderá la tramitación del Tratado o Convenio hasta la decisión del Tribunal. En el caso de que ésta fuese negativa, se continuará el procedimiento

requirement is met, the processing of the Treaty or Agreement will be suspended until the decision of the Court is taken. In the event that this is a negative decision, the procedure will be continued.

3. Formalizing consent

Another issue that arises is the competent body to formalize the withdrawal? Once the authorization is carried out and its approval by the Parliament, the King is the authority vested with the power of signing the instrument of denunciation. Article 96.2 does not clarify this matter, even if it can be deduced from a systematic analysis of the Constitution, since article 63.2⁵⁴ of the Constitution requires that the King manifest the consent of the State to be bound internationally by means of treaties, in accordance with the Spanish Constitution and the laws.

4. The participation of Autonomous Communities

One last issue arising from the procedure of withdrawal following article 94.1 is the issue of the participation of the Autonomous Communities (*Comunidades Autónomas*). The lack of power given to the Senate as a territorial body, is paralleled to the almost to none role that the Autonomous Communities play in matters of international affairs. In the Spanish constituent process nobody came to propose the direct participation of the Autonomous Communities in the conclusion of Treaties⁵⁵. According to article 149.1.3 of the Constitution, the State has exclusive competence on the following issues: [...] 3. International relations⁵⁶. This issue has been of much concern, due to the pressure of autonomous regions and entities to have a say in international law. In this sense, this had led to proposals to reform the Constitution and give equal powers to the Senate as a Chamber of territorial representation, problems relating to the division of competences, since Autonomous Communities will have a direct interest or will be affected by international treaties. And last, but not least, the lack of power granted by the Constitution to the Senate, was from the very beginning, also due to the fact that it was very poorly handled by the authorities, being one of the factors leading to a growing tension between the Central Government (the

⁵⁴ Article 63.2 Al Rey corresponde manifestar el consentimiento del Estado para obligarse internacionalmente por medio de tratados, de conformidad con la Constitución y las leyes

⁵⁵ See Remiro Brotons, A., “artículos 93 y 94”, vid supra note 40, p. 575.

⁵⁶ El Estado tiene competencia exclusiva sobre las siguientes materias: 3ª Relaciones internacionales.

negatively referred to “Gobierno de Madrid”) and Autonomous Governments, which has led in some cases to the rise of self-determination and nationalistic movements⁵⁷.

The preliminary statements of Law 25/2014 clearly indicates that the State has exclusive jurisdiction in matters of international relations that, based on a well-established jurisprudence of the Constitutional Court, includes at its core precisely the ability to celebrate international treaties, the so-called *ius ad tractatum*. However, the Autonomous Communities are competent to carry out certain external activities, among which, for example, the celebration of non-normative international agreements. They also have competence to conclude international administrative agreements, in the realization or execution of a treaty. They also enjoy competences in other aspects of external action that also have consequences for the State’s own foreign policy in terms of the conclusion of international treaties and which must be subject to regulation in order to guarantee their adequate insertion within the exclusive competence of the State⁵⁸. According to the Constitution, the central organs of the State can assume international obligations in matters of the exclusive competence of an Autonomous Community, without their participation, since, for example, according to article 93, it is possible to transfer their exercise to an international organization, through an organic law of authorization as a special mechanism for modifying the Statutes of the Communities.⁵⁹

However, formulas have been considered to involve the Autonomous Communities with the decision-making process of the State within the European Union.⁶⁰ In the statutory reforms of 2006 practically all of the new Statutes of the Autonomous Communities are expressly provided, and in general with a separate chapter on the external action, their participation as "regions of Europe" in the formation of the State's negotiating position before the European Union, in Spanish delegations before the European institutions and, especially, before the Council, as well as the possibility of directing to the State the observations and proposals that they deem appropriate and the right to be informed of such projects. And they maintain the foresight, contained since the eighties, to develop and execute the right of the European Union in the areas of its competence⁶¹. The institutionalized

⁵⁷This issue has been more latent recently in the Autonomous Community of Cataluña, where the rise of a movement claiming for self-determination and nationalism, and the clash with nationalistic claims by the Central Government has led to the escalation of tension, leading to an internal conflict.

⁵⁸ Exposición de Motivos II of Law 25/2014

⁵⁹ Remiro Brotons, A., “artículos 93 y 94”, vid supra note 40, p. 575.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ Mangas Martín, A., and Liñán Noguerras, J. (2017). *Instituciones y derecho de la Unión Europea*. Tecnos. p. 490

and specific multilateral coordination is carried out through the Conference for Affairs Related to the European Union (CARUE). A forum specialized in matters of the Union, formed by the political leaders of the Autonomous Communities and the central Government, to debate together the respective positions and to decant the position of Spain in the institutions with governmental presence. Within CARUE, the Agreement on the internal participation of the Autonomous Communities in European Community Affairs was adopted in 1994 through the Sectoral Conferences. This Agreement properly contains the framework procedure for participation when issues on the Union are discussed. When the matter of the Union affects exclusively the reserved powers of the State and the Autonomous Communities invoke their interest in this matter, the Administration will inform them in a timely manner within the framework of the Sectoral Conference. The law of treaties is the exclusive competence of the State and therefore the State will only have to inform the Autonomous Community in case of wanting to denounce the Treaties of the European Union.⁶²

2. Constitutional admissibility of referendums: legal effects and requirements

Referendums in Spain have been and are a very complex and controversial institution. As a concept, it was defined by the Constitutional Court in its decision of September 11, 2008 as an instrument of direct and political participation and more specifically as a kind of “popular consultation”⁶³. This section will consider the constitutional clauses relative to the possibility to conduct a referendum, the legal effects of referendums and the requirements that permit to conduct such popular consultations.

The Spanish Constitution permits different forms of direct participation. Article 9.2 expressly states that “[i]t is up to the public authorities [...] to facilitate the participation of all citizens in political, economic, cultural and social life”⁶⁴ and article 23.1 of the Constitution recognizes

⁶² *Ibid.*, p. 491-492. On the participation of Autonomous Communities in European Union matters see: Martín y Pérez de Nanclares, J, (2005), *Comunidades Autónomas y Unión Europea: Hacia una Mejora de la Participación Directa de las Comunidades Autónomas en el Proceso Decisorio Comunitario*. *Revista de Derecho Comunitario*, p. 759-805.

⁶³ This decision solved a controversy surrounding the alleged unconstitutionality filed against the Law of the Basque Parliament 9/2008, of June 27, on the convocation and regulation of a popular referendum for the purpose of gathering public opinion in the Autonomous Basque Country on the opening of a negotiation process to achieve peace and political normalization. Constitutional Court, Decision 103/2008, of 11th September, (BOE núm. 245, de 10 de Octubre de 2008) <http://hj.tribunalconstitucional.es/de/Resolucion/Show/6335>

⁶⁴ Artículo 9. 2. Corresponde a los poderes públicos promover las condiciones para que la libertad y la igualdad del individuo y de los grupos en que se integra sean reales y efectivas; remover los obstáculos que impidan o dificulten su plenitud y facilitar la participación de todos los ciudadanos en la vida política, económica, cultural y social.

among the fundamental rights of citizens the “participation in public affairs, directly or through representatives freely elected in periodic elections by universal suffrage”⁶⁵. To engage in the forms participation, the Constitutional text authorizes different types of referendums. Article 62 c) and article 92 set out the general framework applicable to referendums.⁶⁶ Article 92 sets out the basic framework for a consultative referendum stating that “[p]olitical decisions of special importance may be submitted to a consultative referendum of all citizens. The referendum will be convened by the King, on the proposal of the President of the Government, previously authorized by the Congress of Deputies. An organic law will regulate the conditions and procedure of the different modalities of referendum foreseen in this Constitution”⁶⁷. This law was finally adopted in 1980 through the Organic Law 2/1980⁶⁸.

Following the general framework, article 149.1.32 regulates the case of popular consultations. It gives the State the exclusive competence to authorize the call for popular consultations through referendum⁶⁹. The Constitution only requires that the authorization for popular consultations is of exclusive competence, yet doesn’t really specify what a popular consultation is. There has been much criticism of the ambiguity and unclear regulation of this type of referendum and the differences in relation to article 92.3 referendums. The Organic Law 2/1980 included a supplementary provision which excludes this type of referendum from the Law. The provision dictates that the provisions of the Law do not reach in their regulation popular consultations that may be held by the City Councils (*Ayuntamientos*), related to relevant matters of a municipal nature, in their respective territories, in accordance with the Local Regime legislation, and safe, in any case, the exclusive competence of the State for its authorization. It is unclear whether this

⁶⁵ Artículo 23. 1. Los ciudadanos tienen el derecho a participar en los asuntos públicos, directamente o por medio de representantes, libremente elegidos en elecciones periódicas por sufragio universal

⁶⁶ Linde Paniagua, E., “Artículo 92: Referendum”, in en Oscar Alzaga Villaamil, O., 2006, *Comentarios a la Constitución Española*, Edersa.

⁶⁷ Artículo 92

1. Las decisiones políticas de especial trascendencia podrán ser sometidas a referéndum consultivo de todos los ciudadanos.

2. El referéndum será convocado por el Rey, mediante propuesta del Presidente del Gobierno, previamente autorizada por el Congreso de los Diputados.

3. Una ley orgánica regulará las condiciones y el procedimiento de las distintas modalidades de referéndum previstas en esta Constitución

⁶⁸ Ley Orgánica 2/1980, de 18 de enero, sobre regulación de las distintas modalidades de referéndum, «BOE» núm. 20, de 23/01/1980.

⁶⁹ Artículo 149. 1. El Estado tiene competencia exclusiva sobre las siguientes materias: [...] 32.^a Autorización para la convocatoria de consultas populares por vía de referéndum.

supplementary provision relates to article 149.1. 32 and has been very contested by doctrine since it excludes these types of referendums from the scope of the law⁷⁰.

Referendums are also permitted in the Constitution in relation to the framework of the autonomic process. Articles 151.1 permits referendums for the ratification of the autonomic initiative; 151.2 for the approval of the Statutes of Autonomy (*Estatutos de Autonomía*); 152.2 referendum required for the statutory reform of the Statutes and The Fourth Transitory Provision, article 1 (*Disposición Transicional Cuarta*), referendum required in order to a possible incorporation of Navarra to the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country.

Likewise, two types of referendum are included in articles 167.3 and 168.3 to permit a constitutional reform. Article 167.3 includes the possibility to conduct a referendum, once a constitutional reform has been approved by the Parliament, as long as the Parliament requests the referendum by one tenth of the members of either of the Chambers, within fifteen days following its approval. Article 168.3 allows for a referendum when a total revision of the Constitution or a partial revision affecting the Preliminary Title, the Second Chapter, First Section of Title I, or Title II is proposed. This proposal shall be approved by a majority of two thirds of each Chamber and will lead to the immediate dissolution of the Parliament. Once elected a new Parliament, the latter must ratify the decision and proceed to the study of the new constitutional text, which must be approved by a two-thirds majority of both Chambers. Once the reform has been approved by the new Parliament, it will be submitted to a referendum for ratification.

Referendums permitted in the Constitution can be divided into two groups: facultative and compulsory. Non mandatory are referendums under article 92 and the one for constitutional reform in article 167.3. Their conclusion is not a mandatory requirement for the adoption of the political decision or to conclude the constitutional reform. Those which are compulsory and an essential element of the process taking place, and binding, are the referendums under articles 151 and 152, the Fourth Transitory Provision and the referendum for the constitutional reform in article 168.⁷¹

The referendum on the withdrawal from the European Union would be admissible under article 92 of the Constitution. To date, only two national consultative referendums have been held under Article 92: the one regarding the permanence of Spain in North Atlantic Alliance and the one

⁷⁰ Linde Paniagua, E., “Artículo 92: Referendum”, *vid supra* note 66, p. 465-467

⁷¹ *Ibid.*, p. 477-478.

celebrated for the ratification by Spain of the Treaty establishing a Constitution for Europe, signed in Rome on October 29, 2004. Both of these referendums were carried out through article 92 of the Constitution and followed the procedure established in the Organic law 2/1980, of January 18th. The result of the referendum, held on March 12, 1986, was favorable to the Government's proposal, the “yes” to approve a Treaty establishing a Constitution for Europe won with 77% of the votes.⁷²

Where there be a referendum on withdrawal from the European Union, article 92 clearly indicates its consultative nature, meaning, not legally binding, used for advisory purposes. Yet, the drafting of article 92 of the Constitution is very ambiguous. It is unclear what the scope of “political decisions of special importance” is. Some authors have argued that by political decisions, the Constitution is indicating that the body responsible to propose an article 92 referendum is the Government⁷³. Yet the scope of consultative referenda, related to what can be consulted, under article 92, is very unclear⁷⁴. Reference to the Organic Law 2/1980, of January 18th can help shed some light on the contours of consultative referenda, yet many issues remain unclear and unresolved.⁷⁵

In order for this type of referendum to be constitutional, article 92 indicates that the referendum will be convened by the King, on the proposal of the President of the Government, previously authorized by the Congress of Deputies. It is the President the one endowed with the initiative. This initiative is exclusive and once it has been proposed, it will need to be authorized by the Congress of Deputies. Article 6 of the 2/1980 Organic Law requires that “[t]he consultative referendum provided for in article ninety-two of the Constitution shall require the prior authorization of the Congress of Deputies by an absolute majority, at the request of the President of the Government. This request must contain the exact terms in which the query is to be formulated”⁷⁶. Authorization hence will require absolute majority of the Chamber and must

⁷² <http://www.congreso.es/consti/constitucion/indice/sinopsis/sinopsis.jsp?art=92&tipo=2>

⁷³ Linde, E., “Artículo 92: Referendum”, *vid supra* note 66, p. 463-464.

⁷⁴ *Ibid*

⁷⁵ Linde Paniagua, E., & Herrero Lera, M. (1980). Comentario a la Ley orgánica de modalidades de referéndum. *Revista de Derecho político*, (6), 83-105.

⁷⁶ Artículo 6: El referéndum consultivo previsto en el artículo noventa y dos de la Constitución requerirá la previa autorización del Congreso de los Diputados por mayoría absoluta, a solicitud del Presidente del Gobierno. Dicha solicitud deberá contener los términos exactos en que haya de formularse la consulta.

contain the exact terms in which the query is to be formulated. The Regulation of the Congress of Deputies specifies the procedure to authorize consultative referendums in Chapter two.

Once authorized, it will be the King the competent body to convene the referendum by Royal Decree agreed upon by the Council of Ministers and endorsed by its President. This role is specifically recognized in article 2.2.e) of the Law 50/1997, of November 27th.⁷⁷

Article 3 of the Organic Law 2/1980 requires that the Royal Decree has to contain the full text of the draft provision or, where appropriate, the political decision that is the subject of the consultation; clearly indicate the question or questions to be answered by the Electoral Body convened and determine the date on which the vote is to be held, which must take place between thirty and one hundred and twenty days after the date of publication of the Royal Decree itself. The Royal Decree calling for the referendum will be published in the "Official State Gazette" and will be inserted in full in the "Official Gazettes" of all the Spanish provinces or of the Autonomous Communities and of the provinces affected by the celebration; likewise, it must be disseminated in all newspapers published in them and in those with the largest circulation in Spain within five calendar days following its publication in the "Official State Gazette"; It will also be posted on the notice boards of all the affected municipalities, as well as in all diplomatic and consular representations, and will be broadcasted on radio and television.

The Organic Law regulates as well a common procedure for all types of referendums in articles 11 to 19. Article 11 indicates that the procedure will be subject to the general electoral regime regulated by the Organic Law 5/1985, of 19th June in what is applicable and does not oppose the Organic Law 2/1980. It includes as well provisions on the constitution and functions of the Electoral Boards (articles 12 and 13), the propaganda campaign (articles 14 and 15), the voting, the scrutiny and the proclamation of results (articles 16 to 18), and on the claims and appeals (article 19).

Article 4.1 of the Organic Law 2/1980 requires that a referendum cannot be held in any of its modalities during states of exception in any of the territorial areas in which the consultation is held or in the ninety days after its removal. If, on the date of the declaration of said states, a referendum is called, its celebration shall be suspended, which shall be subject to a new convocation.

⁷⁷ Ley 50/1997, de 27 de noviembre, del Gobierno. «BOE» núm. 285, de 28/11/1997.

There are many issues left unresolved in the law and that have generated much controversy. It is clear from the drafting of the law the mistrust towards the referendum as a mechanism by the constituent authorities⁷⁸. First, there is no reference in the Constitution or in the Organic Law to the percentage of vote the referendum must receive in order for it to be considered valid. Second, from an analysis of the territorial and the personal scope of consultative referendums, it seems that those having nationality would be allowed to vote, based on articles 13.2 and 23.1 of the Spanish Constitution, but it is unclear whether it can have a smaller territorial and personal scope. Article 5.1 of the Organic Law requires that referendum will be decided by universal, free, equal, direct and secret suffrage in the area corresponding to the consultation and the electoral law does not solve this controversy. Third, neither the Constitution nor the Law gives any guidance on whether, if the referendum were to be negative or positive, the legal consequences it would entail. If the Government submits a question for referendum, and the answer is supportive, then the Government will be backed by the population and will proceed. The problem arises when the people oppose the decision by voting negatively to the question posed through referendum. There is no answer in the law, presumably the Government will have to refrain from its decision, yet it is not so clear. Fourth, an important matter, but yet unanswered presently is whether, in case of an unclear result, or a result not backed by a high majority of the population or marked drastically by different sectors of the population or territorial entities, like the one we are experiencing recently in the United Kingdom, there is no guidance nor regulation on whether the Government can repeat the referendum as many times as it wishes, if it is unhappy with the turnout. Fifth, it is clear from the legal framework, the lack of inclusion of the Senate from the process. Last, article 14 of the Organic Law permits that during the propaganda campaign, the media of public ownership must grant free spaces, yet only the political groups with representation in the Parliament will be entitled to the use of these free spaces⁷⁹. This evidently is a matter of much controversy since this law will

⁷⁸ Linde Paniagua, E., "Artículo 92: Referendum", *vid supra* note 66, p. 474.

⁷⁹ The Constitutional Court has ratified this limitation in its decisión 63/1987, of 20th May: This norm according to the Court, "ciertamente, no es la única concebible dentro el marco constitucional", tiene un sólido fundamento en su orientación a actualizar la previsión genérica del artículo 20.3 de la Constitución. "Pretende allí la Norma Fundamental que por la Ley se asegure a los grupos sociales y políticos "significativos" su acceso a los medios públicos de los que ahora se trata y es de todo punto claro que esa cualificación constitucional -la "significación" por la "representación" en las Cámaras- no la muestran los grupos políticos sino cuando los mismos se hallen presentes en el Parlamento a resultas de los sufragios que en su día recabaron ante el cuerpo electoral, porque sólo en tal caso esa presencia parlamentaria que la Ley exige será indicativa -"significativa", en la expresión constitucional- del arraigo o implantación del grupo en cuestión entre el electorado. Fuera de esta hipótesis, que es la común, la ulterior integración de parlamentarios en un grupo político que no presentó candidatos propios en las anteriores elecciones, o que no logró

leave out political groups that do not have representation in Parliament. In this sense, how representative these political parties need to be in Parliament is unclear and will also entail that many political parties, not represented in Parliament but representative in Autonomous Communities or other electoral constituency, where the referendum would be taking place, would be excluded.⁸⁰

IV. Public opinion on Spain's withdrawal from the European Union

1. Is withdrawal from the European Union a topic of discussion in Spain?

Spain's withdrawal from the European Union isn't presently a topic of discussion. Support of the European Union remains high⁸¹. Nevertheless, Brexit is a topic of discussion among politicians and academics for many different issues. Firstly, politicians and academics interested in the phenomena of stepping out of international organization have queried on the reasons for support and the decline of IO's legitimacy and support in Europe and the whole European Union project.⁸²

Secondly, Brexit has been mainly discussed in relation to the effects it might have on Spain. In this sense, one of the major concerns is how Brexit will affect Spain's economy, since Spain has very strong connections with the United Kingdom, mainly due to movement of persons, because of tourism and migration, and also economic interests. In this sense, Spanish economy will be damaged by Brexit since the UK is the fourth most important market for exports of Spanish products. Services will also be affected by Brexit, since the United Kingdom is the main market for Spanish tourism services. Migratory flows are also important for both countries. Spain receives a high percentage of British, mainly elderly, that live part of their year in Spain and depend heavily

conseguir para ellos el apoyo del cuerpo electoral, podrá ser relevante a efectos de la organización y funcionamiento interno de las Cámaras, según dispongan sus reglamentos, pero no en lo relativo a la determinación de la significación del grupo mismo, que no recabó o no obtuvo de los ciudadanos los sufragios que hubieran podido llevarle como organización en la que se hubieran encuadrado candidatos electos, hasta las instituciones públicas representativas". Constitutional Court 63/1987, of 20th May (BOE núm. 134, de 05 de junio de 1987), Fundamento Jurídico 7.

⁸⁰ On the distribution of seats in the Spanish Congress and the effects see: de Córdoba, G. F., & Penadés, A. (2009). Institutionalizing uncertainty: the choice of electoral formulas. *Public Choice*, 141(3-4), 391-403. Penadés de la Cruz, Alberto. 2006 "The institutional preferences of early socialists parties: choosing rules for government", en Maravall, J. M. y I. Sánchez-Cuenca (eds.), *Controlling governments: Voters, Institutions and Accountability*, New York: Cambridge University Press; Penadés de la Cruz, Alberto. 2006 "La difícil ciencia de los orígenes de los sistemas electorales", *Revista de Estudios Políticos*, 131: 193-218.

⁸¹ As will be analyzed below

⁸² Mangas Martín, A. (2016). Postbrexit: una Europa confusa, entre el desánimo y la incertidumbre. *Revista de Derecho Comunitario Europeo*, 20(54), 427-437; Izaguirre, J. L. (2018). Organizaciones internacionales: comunicar la utilidad. *Comillas Journal of International Relations*, (12), 28-37.

on Spanish social security. Britain is a market on the contrary mainly for youth seeking work opportunities. The United Kingdom is also the main destination for foreign direct investment outflows and accounts for 14% of total Spanish foreign direct investment outflows. For its part, the United Kingdom is the fifth largest investor in Spain, where it has significant investments in telecommunications and tobacco sectors. Spanish investment in the financial sector of the United Kingdom is especially important. Of all the European countries, the Spanish banking sector has the largest investments in the private banking sector in the United Kingdom, only behind the US.⁸³

But one of the most discussed and a pending issue for Spain, and that following the Brexit, has been at center stage of academic discussion is the question of Gibraltar. Once the United Kingdom leaves the European Union, Gibraltar will also. As the Council of Europe has indicated, “on the date on which the withdrawal takes effect, the Treaties shall cease to apply to the United Kingdom, to its overseas countries and territories currently associated with the Union and to territories whose external relations the Kingdom assumes”.⁸⁴ Although Gibraltar is not expressly mentioned, it is clear that this autonomous territory pending decolonization fits without doubt in the territorial scope of “the territories whose external relations the United Kingdom assumes” in the sense of the already described article 355.3.⁸⁵

The withdrawal of the United Kingdom from the European Union will awaken the Treaty of Utrecht, of July 13, 1713, subscribed by the Crowns of Spain and England, within the framework of a new model of relationship between Spain and the United Kingdom outside the European Union⁸⁶. It is from this moment that an opportunity emerges to try to find a reasonable solution to

⁸³ On the effects of Brexit on the Spanish economy see: Greenwood, N. (2016). Referéndum de Reino Unido sobre la permanencia en la UE: consecuencias para las economías británica, de la UE y española. *Cuadernos de Información Económica*, (252), 105-115. Gavira, J. M. (2017). Brexit: Efectos económicos en un escenario incierto. *La Albolafia: Revista de Humanidades y Cultura*, (12), 55-74. Salvador Llaudes, Ignacio Molina, Miguel Otero Iglesias and Federico Steinberg. Elcano Policy Paper 3/2018 - 15/6/2018. Spain and the prospect of Brexit http://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/wps/portal/rielcano_en/contenido?WCM_GLOBAL_CONTEXT=/elcano/elcano_in/zonas_in/Policy-Paper-2018-Spain-prospect-Brexit.

⁸⁴ European Council, EUCO XT 20004/17, 29th April 2017, note 4, general orientation 4.

⁸⁵ Martín y Pérez de Nanclares, J., “Brexit y Gibraltar: la cosoberanía como posible solución de la controversia sobre Gibraltar: un acer-camiento jurídico en el contexto del Brexit”, en Martín Martínez, M.M., y Martín y Pérez de Nanclares, J., (Coord.) 2017, *El Brexit y Gibraltar: Un reto con oportunidades conjuntas*, 11-37

⁸⁶ Escobar Hernández, C. (2016). Brexit: Algunas Reflexiones Desde el Derecho Internacional. *Revista Española de Derecho Internacional*, p. 21-22.

the old dispute in Gibraltar⁸⁷, also we will wake up from the anesthesia that the European Union has injected this territorial conflict with.⁸⁸

Gibraltar is a non-self-governing territory, declared by the United Nations⁸⁹. Notwithstanding the Spanish proposal to have a joint sovereignty⁹⁰, the legal framework for this territory requires that the solution of the dispute of Gibraltar be solved by both Spain and the United Kingdom, taking into account the interests of the population. Hence any agreement on the territory of Gibraltar will need the consent of both the United Kingdom and Spain⁹¹. This has been recognized by the United Nations in their Resolutions⁹² and by the Council of the European Union.⁹³

2. Political parties that support the withdrawal of the State from the European Union

Political groups supporting the withdrawal from Brexit aren't very representative, yet lately, have been the focus of much attention, since they have played an important role when forming coalitions in Cataluña and in Andalucía.

The CUP (*Candidatura d'Unitat Popular*) is a political assembly organization with a presence in the Catalan countries and that works for an independent, socialist, ecologically sustainable, territorially balanced and liberated country from any form of patriarchal domination. The Candidature of the People's Unity (CUP) is articulated as a political tool for all those people and groups with a transforming and groundbreaking will that fight for the freedom of the Catalan people, with the intention of being a space of confluence of the popular movements, in the fight

⁸⁷ Much debated in Spanish doctrine. See: Andrés Sáenz de Santa María, P., «Gibraltar y el Derecho de la descolonización», *Cuadernos de Gibraltar-Gibraltar Reports* núm. 1, 2015, pp. 89-106; Remiro Brotons, A., «Regreso a Gibraltar: acuerdos y desacuerdos hispano-británicos», *Revista Jurídica de la Universidad Autónoma de Madrid*, vol. 10, 2004, pp. 133-182; Valle Gálvez, A. del, «¿De verdad cedimos el Peñón? Opciones estratégicas de España sobre Gibraltar a los 300 años del Tratado de Utrecht», *Revista Española de Derecho Internacional* vol. LXV, 2013, pp. 117-156.

⁸⁸ Mangas Martín, A. (2016). ¿Brexit? Escenarios internacionales y Gibraltar. *Vid supra* note 28, p. 14

⁸⁹ <http://www.un.org/en/decolonization/pdf/Gibraltar2017.pdf>

⁹⁰ On this proposal see: Andrés Sáenz de Santa María, P. (2017). The new Spanish proposal for joint sovereignty: Gibraltar at the post-Brexit crossroads. *Revista General de Derecho Europeo*.

⁹¹ Andrés Sáenz de Santamaría, P., "Brexit y Gibraltar: la Perspectiva de Naciones Unidas" en Martín Martínez, M.M., y Martín y Pérez de Nanclares, J., (Coord.) 2017, *El Brexit y Gibraltar: Un reto con oportunidades conjuntas*, p. 51

⁹² Resolution 1514 (XV), of December 14, 1960, Resolution 2070 (XX), of December 16, 1965; Resolution 2353 (XXII), of December 19, 1967; Resolution 2429 (XXIII) of December 18, 1968). See Martín y Pérez de Nanclares, J., "Brexit y Gibraltar: la soberanía compartida como posible solución de la controversia", *Ibid*, p. 23

⁹³ [u]na vez que el Reino Unido haya abandonado la Unión, ningún acuerdo entre la UE y el Reino Unido podrá aplicarse al territorio de Gibraltar sin acuerdo entre el Reino de España y el Reino Unido". CONSEJO EUROPEO: Reunión extraordinaria del Consejo Europeo (art. 50) (29 de abril de 2017)-Orientaciones, Bruselas 29 de abril de 2017 (OR-en), EUCO XT 20004/17, BXT 10, CO EUR 5, CONCL 2, <http://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/XT-20004-2017-INIT/es/pdf>, par. 24.

for the national and social liberation of the Países Catalanes⁹⁴. In their electoral program they call for the establishment of a Republic, the aggressiveness of the Spanish state and the complicity of the European Union⁹⁵. CUP believes that the economic crisis is a product of the capitalist and patriarchal system, based on the exploitation of the working class, the exploitation of women , dispossession and inequality, and directed by European institutions and supported by the political and economic elites⁹⁶. The CUP believes that the centralistic logic of the Spanish state is parallel to the politics of the European Union and the Troika⁹⁷, and is adjacent to the absorption of sovereignty from the States on behalf of the European Union⁹⁸. The program states expressly that the CUP-CC repeals forming part of the European Union, the Euro, NATO, and the European military⁹⁹.

Another political party showing a clear anti-European position and has lately been at the center of attention is VOX. VOX is an extreme right political party. This party, in the last elections in Andalucía, received an increased support, winning 12 seats in the regional Parliament¹⁰⁰. Its program defends national sovereignty over the European Union. VOX defends the promotion of a new European treaty in Brussels, along the lines advocated by the countries of the Visegrad group in terms of borders, national sovereignty and respect for the values of European culture, and to considerably increase the weight of Spain in the decision-making, at least as much as the Treaty of Nice¹⁰¹. Reduction of European political spending, eliminate duplication and agencies that interfere in national sovereignty. Exclusivity of the State, in relation to international relations, suppression of all foreign political representation of regions or municipalities.¹⁰² VOX also supports bilateralism in international relations, abandoning supranational organizations if they are contrary to the interests of Spain, and the re-evaluation of the Spanish contribution to these bodies.¹⁰³

⁹⁴ <http://cup.cat/que-es-la-cup-cast>

⁹⁵ <http://cup.cat/sites/default/files/programaelectoralcup21d.pdf>

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, par. 3.

⁹⁷ *Ibid*, par. 6

⁹⁸ *Ibid*.

⁹⁹ *Ibid*, par 269

¹⁰⁰ On the reasons why VOX has risen so much in Andalucía: <http://www.rtve.es/noticias/20181203/claves-del-exito-vox-andalucia-cataluna-descontento-derecha-espanola-precedentes-europeos/1847583.shtml>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.voxespana.es/programa-electoral-vox>, par. 96

¹⁰² *Ibid*, 97.

¹⁰³ *Ibid*, 99.

Another party that suggests the withdrawal of Spain from the EU is Spain 2000, another extreme right wing movement, with very little support. They present themselves as a Spanish nationalist movement and as such, do not accept, therefore, foreign impositions. Their program is based on the following premises “Yes to Europe, not to the European Union [...] The current European Union is a supranational entity that, through legislation issued by a European Parliament, marks the paths to be taken by the member states, favoring the most powerful states in their policies. This entity has been badly conceived from the start, as it is a free-market system between states [...] the existing borders have disappeared, favoring the mobility of its inhabitants, among them the criminals, which means that there is currently complete lack of control on behalf of the authorities in these movements, as well as the increase in the danger that these can entail for the security of a country [...] our country has only one possibility to position itself internationally as a benchmark, basing its economy on tourism, a sector subject to fashion and distant from a productive economy. This sector also has a temporary nature, which means that the jobs subject to it are very seasonal and only its incidence on the figures of active population in the summer season is noted, [t]he disappearance of borders, following the global economic model that dominates the world today, has led to the disappearance of tariffs that encumber the entry of European products that enter our country, which has caused the economy to be resentful in the competition with products from other countries [...] In addition, since the year 2002, with the arrival of the euro, there has been a loss of monetary sovereignty by the member states, which does not allow, for example, devaluations of the national currency, leaving the country subject to the interests of other countries that may have a greater specific weight within the Union [...] The impossibility of declaring odious debts contracted by the political class backed by the general interest and prioritizing the payment of the debt to other states, such as Germany, is causing the loss of public services in many European regions, as well as a cheapening of the labor that is making the average worker lose purchasing power and their quality of life has been greatly reduced. The immediate consequence of this is that consumption, the fundamental economic base of the capitalist systems, that dominates the European Union, has plummeted, producing a devastating effect on employment figures [...] The only solution for European reconstruction and to destroy this globalizing European Union and the markets, is the reconstruction of Europe as a confederation of

National States, without any cession of sovereignty by the members, as the best way to ensure the future of a geographical group linked by cultural, social and historical links.¹⁰⁴

These political parties still have low electoral support. Nevertheless there has been a recent rise of one of these groups. The motives behind the rise of these parties lie in the economic crisis experienced by Spain, the widespread corruption practices of the two traditional political parties and the Catalan question, are *inter alia* some of the reasons portrayed in the media. Attention needs to be paid to this phenomenon, not only experienced in Spain but globally, mainly due to their nationalist, racist, misogynist, homophobic and xenophobic political agendas which are a threat to the most fundamental human rights.

3. Is civil society in Spain against the European Union?

Civil society in Spain shows varied attitudes towards the European Union, but of general support. The Standard Eurobarometer of Autumn (SEA) 2018 survey showed that more than half of Europeans feel attached to the European Union and to Europe. A majority of respondents in 19 EU Member States, compared with 16 in spring 2017, showed to feel attached to the European Union.¹⁰⁵ Since spring 2017, attachment to the European Union increased, led by Spain with 71% of participants showing attachment.¹⁰⁶ The SEA showed that in the 28 Member States, respondents were more likely to feel attached to Europe than to the European Union. However, the difference was negligible in Spain, where 73% showed attachment to the EU and 71% to Europe.¹⁰⁷ In relation to citizenship, a majority of respondents felt that they were citizens of the EU in 27 Member States. The study was led by Luxembourg and Spain, where 88% of the participants showed to feel that they were citizens of the EU¹⁰⁸. In terms of evolutions since spring 2017, the SEA showed that the sense of European citizenship has gained ground in 14 Member States, most markedly in Spain, with 82% of participants showing a sense of EU citizenship¹⁰⁹ pointing to the “rule of law” and the “economy” as the factors, which do the most to create a feeling of community.¹¹⁰

¹⁰⁴ <http://espana2000.org/programa-politico/>

¹⁰⁵ European Commission, Standard Eurobarometer 88 Autumn 2017, <https://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion/.../82871>, p. 11.

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 14.

¹⁰⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 32.

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 37.

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 45.

V. Conclusions

This article has studied the legal framework that would apply in Spain, were the country to decide to withdraw from the European Union. For this purpose, the article has departed from an analysis of the Constitutional foundations of a hypothetical withdrawal and has focused on issues left unresolved by the Constitution, which left legal gaps, later on covered by Law 25/2014. Nevertheless were Spain to decide to withdraw, it is unclear from the present legal framework, what would happen with secondary law and third country agreements, which will have become internal law. In this sense, following the precedent of Brexit, maybe a new category, like the one created by the Exit Agreement between the United Kingdom and the European Union, as “retained EU law” will be articulated. As well, there is lack of clarity surrounding the jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice that will be accorded, were Spain wish to withdraw. Yet, the article argues in favour of maintaining the jurisdiction of the European Court of Justice on those matters which are European Union rights and obligations “retained”, for the purposes of international cooperation.

After considering the constitutional framework, the article moves on to analyse the constitutional obstacles to withdraw from the European Union. To this end, the different stages are outlined, and analysed. Issues are uncovered surrounding this procedure such as: the barring of popular initiative in international matters, *i.e.* the denunciation of an international treaty; the unequal power given to the Congress and the Senate in matters of International Law, carefully crafted and embedded in the procedure to follow when concluding or denouncing Treaties.

The unequal power given to the Senate, entailing the invisibility of the voice of the territorial entities in matters of International Law is mirrored by the very soft power given to the Autonomous Communities in matters of International Affairs. The direct participation of the Autonomous Communities in the conclusion of treaties was obliterated in the Spanish Constitution. This task was given exclusively to the State. However, within the European Union, the Autonomous Communities have been granted progressively direct participation in the States’ negotiating position, in relation to those matters that fall under their exclusive competence, yet, in matters of denunciation, which involve international affairs, the State will only be required to inform them.

Shifting the focus of attention on the legal framework and procedure that permits a hypothetical withdrawal, the study engages in an analysis of the possibility to conduct a hypothetical referendum in Spain, regarding a withdrawal from the European Union. To this end, the different

types of referendum are outlined, those that are consultative and those that are binding. In relation to the withdrawal from the European Union, the framework applicable to the possibility to conduct a referendum on this matter is clear but not lacking controversy, which shows a clear mistrust for this mechanism by the Spanish constitutional drafting authorities. First, the ambiguity and unclear regulation of the so-called “popular consultations” under article 149.1.32 of the Constitution, which has left this mechanism in a legal vacuum. Second, withdrawing from the European Union would most likely be processed under article 92, which is non-mandatory, meaning not legally binding and used for consultative purposes, yet this legal formula leaves many issues unresolved. First, the scope of these referendums since “political decisions of special importance” is clearly broad terminology. Taking into account previous practice, consultations on leaving the European Union would fall into this category, since the referendum on the accession of Spain to the European Union was considered a political decision of special importance. Second, there is no reference to the percentage of vote the referendum needs to receive to be considered valid. Third, the territorial and personal scope of the referendum is clearly an unaddressed matter, in relation to whether referendums under article 92 could be carried out in territorial entities smaller than the State and in relation to the population that could participate in them. Fourth, if the vote were to be “no” to leave the European Union, it is ambiguous whether the Government would be bound by such final outcome. Fifth, whether the referendum can be repeated in case a result is uncertain or unforeseen and contrary to what is thought to be best for the interest of the State. Sixth, the lack of inclusion of the Senate from the process and last, the space given to political groups with representation in Parliament to use free spaces for the purposes of propaganda, clearly evidence the constitutional barriers posed to the territorial entities and to the views of political parties without representation in Parliament but representative in local districts and Autonomous Communities.

Finally, the article moves on to address the issue of public opinion in Spain regarding the possibility of a hypothetical withdrawal. In this sense, the study highlights that the reality of Spain’s withdrawal is not presently a topic of discussion. Brexit has caused much debate in academic circles. Firstly, due to the reality of the loss of legitimacy of IO’s and the reasons for the rise of political movements that have as an aim stepping out of from them. Secondly, the effects that Brexit will cause on the Spanish economy. Thirdly, and a highly disputed issue, the question of Gibraltar, where scholars have highlighted the status of Gibraltar’s as a non-self-governing territory and the requirement that any agreement regarding Gibraltar will need the consent of

Spain, as is required by International Law. Fourthly, the rise of political parties that support the withdrawal of the State from the European Union is a reality in Spain, but with little support at present. Yet some of the political parties have experienced an increased support recently, as a response to collateral circumstances such as the Catalan question, the economic crisis and the widespread corruption of the traditional parties. These anti-EU political parties are in the minority at present, yet their growth needs to be a concern, since their political agendas constitute a threat to the most fundamental values of pluralistic democratic societies and the human rights values they need to cherish. Fifth, the study outlines that civil society in Spain doesn't show a clear mistrust of the European Union. Data shows that Spanish citizens' feelings of attachment to the European Union is high and has increased in the last year, that they feel as attached to the EU and to Europe and that the feelings of citizenship are high and they have increased in the past year.

To conclude, the hypothetical withdrawal of the European Union is possible under the Constitutional Spanish framework. Yet many issues arise in relation to this procedure were it to take place. Many of these issues are subject to much debate, even if "Spexit" is an unlikable possibility, recent developments in political life are starting to put this possibility on the table.